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IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ACUTE PURULENT CHOLANGITIS

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Abstract. The article discusses modern approaches to optimizing surgical treatment of acute purulent cholangitis that develops against the background of choledocholithiasis. The analysis of various methods of decompression of the biliary tract, including endoscopic, laparoscopic and open surgical procedures, was carried out. Special attention is paid to the choice of treatment tactics depending on the degree of inflammatory changes, the severity of intoxication and the functional state of the liver. The criteria for determining the optimal method of surgical intervention are presented, which can reduce the risk of postoperative complications and improve the prognosis in patients.

Keywords: acute purulent cholangitis, choledocholithiasis, surgical treatment, endoscopic decompression

УСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ОСТРЫМ ГНОЙНЫМ ХОЛАНГИТОМ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются современные подходы к оптимизации хирургического лечения острого гнойного холангита, развивающегося на фоне холедохолитиаза. Проведен анализ различных методов декомпрессии желчевыводящих путей, включая эндоскопические, лапароскопические и открытые хирургические вмешательства. Особое внимание уделено выбору тактики лечения в зависимости от степени воспалительных изменений, выраженности интоксикации и функционального состояния печени. Представлены критерии для определения оптимального метода хирургического вмешательства, позволяющие снизить риск послеоперационных осложнений и улучшить прогноз у пациентов.

Ключевые слова: острый гнойный холангит, холедохолитиаз, хирургическое лечение, эндоскопическая декомпрессия

ЎТКИР ЙИРИНГЛИ ХОЛАНГИТ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН БЕМОРЛАРНИ ХИРУРГИК ДАВОЛАШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

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Аннотация. Мақолада холедохолитиаз фонида ривожланадиган ўткир йирингли холангитни жарроҳлик йўли билан даволашни оптималлаштиришнинг замонавий ёндашувлари кўриб чиқилган. Ўт йўллари декомпрессия қилишнинг турли усуллари, шу жумладан эндоскопик, лапароскопик ва очик жарроҳлик аралашувлари таҳлил қилинган. Яллиғланиш ўзгаришларининг даражаси, интоксикациянинг оғирлиги ва жигарнинг функционал ҳолатига қараб даволаш тактикасини танлашга алоҳида эътибор қаратилди. Операциядан кейинги асоратлар

хавфини камайтириш ва беморларда прогнозни яхшилаш имконини берувчи жарроҳлик аралашувининг оптимал усулини аниқлаш мезонлари тақдим этилган.

Калит сўзлар: ўткир йирингли холангит, холедохолитиаз, жарроҳлик даволаш, эндоскопик декомпрессия

Introduction. Acute purulent cholangitis, which occurs against the background of choledocholithiasis, is a serious inflammatory disease of the bile ducts, accompanied by high mortality, reaching up to 60% according to various authors. In the last 15 years, there has been an increase in the frequency of detection of this disease, which is associated with an increase in the number of inflammatory and tumor diseases of the hepatopancreatobiliary zone[1,5].

The main goal of treating acute purulent cholangitis is the rapid decompression of the bile ducts to prevent septic shock and severe sepsis. Improvement of diagnostic and treatment methods, including minimally invasive interventions and staged surgical tactics, contributed to improved treatment outcomes. However, despite achievements, the mortality rate remains significant, which emphasizes the need for further optimization of surgical approaches [2, 4, 7].

Studies conducted in various countries confirm the relevance of this problem. Thus, the works of Russian scientists, such as Bagnenko S.F. and co- authors, indicate an increase in the frequency of acute purulent cholangitis. Ukrainian researchers, including Siplivoy V.A. and colleagues, emphasize the need to improve surgical treatment methods [10]. Thus, optimizing the surgical treatment of acute purulent cholangitis against the background of choledocholithiasis remains a pressing task in modern medicine, requiring further research and the implementation of effective therapeutic strategies [3, 6, 8, 9].

The purpose of the study is to optimize the surgical treatment of acute purulent cholangitis against the background of choledocholithiasis by improving diagnostic criteria, selecting rational surgical tactics, and applying minimally invasive methods to reduce postoperative complications and mortality.

Materials and methods of research. Cases of treatment of patients with acute cholangitis who were admitted to the surgical department of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care of the Samarkand branch between 2018 and 2024 inclusive were analyzed. According to the purpose and objectives of the study, 2 groups of subjects were formed:

I - patients who were treated from 2018 to 2020 inclusive - retrospective part of the work (comparison group). These are patients who have undergone surgery for acute purulent cholangitis of various etiologies.

II - patients who were undergoing treatment from 2021 to 2024 - prospective part of the work (main group). These are patients who were operated on based on the treatment algorithm we developed for patients with acute cholangitis.

Acute purulent cholangitis as a complication of cholelithiasis developed due to choledocholithiasis and chronic calculous cholecystitis in 91 (31.6%), acute calculous cholecystitis and choledocholithiasis in 197 (68.4%) patients, and acute destructive cholecystitis was complicated by various forms of peritonitis in 54 patients (7 disseminated, 47 local) (Table. 1).

Table 1.

Clinical course of acute purulent cholangitis complicated by cholelithiasis

OIT complication		Main group (n=196)	Comparison group (n=92)	Total (n=288)
chronic calculous cholecystitis + choledocholithiasis		59 (30.1%)	32 (34.8%)	91 (31.6%)
acute destructive cholecystitis + choledocholithiasis		137 (69.9%)	60 (65.2%)	197 (68.4%)
including peritonitis	spilled	12.	3.	15.
	local	21.	18.	39.

Total	196.	92.	288.
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As instrumental research methods, radiation and endoscopic methods were used in this study, which play a key role in diagnosing and assessing the condition of patients with acute purulent cholangitis.

To eliminate biliary hypertension in patients, a wide range of surgical methods was used: from minimally invasive to traditional open surgeries. The nature of the performed surgical interventions is presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Performed surgical interventions in the studied groups

Comparison group (n=112)			Main group (n=246)		
Operations		abs. (%)	Operations		abs. (%)
Single-stage interventions (n=106) (94,6%)	open cholecystectomy + external drainage of the gallbladder	30 (26,8%)	Two-stage interventions (n=106) (43,1%)	Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy → endoscopic nasobiliary drainage → laparoscopic cholecystectomy	48 (19,5%)
	Cholecystotomy + cholecystostomy	43 (38,4%)		Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy → endoscopic nasobiliary drainage → open cholecystectomy	21 (8,5%)

	open cholecystectomy + external drainage of the gallbladder, sanitation and drainage of the abdominal cavity	3 (2,7%)		Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy → echinococcectomy from the liver	9 (3,6%)
	laparoscopic cholecystectomy + drainage of the gallbladder through the cystic duct	6 (5,4%)		Percutaneous transhepatic cholangiostomy → hepaticoeunoanastomosis	23 (9,3%)
	open cholecystectomy without decompression of the gallbladder	1 (0,9%)		Percutaneous transhepatic cholangiostomy	5 (2,0%)
	laparoscopic cholecystectomy without decompression of the gallbladder	3 (2,7%)		hepaticoeunoanastomosis	9 (3,6%)
	hepaticoduodenostomosis	5 (4,5%)	Single-stage intervent	open cholecystectomy + external drainage of the gallbladder, sanitation and drainage of the abdominal cavity	12 (4,9%)

	hepaticoeunoanastomosis	7 (6,2%)	ions (n=140) (56,9%)	Hybrid operations		119 (48,4%)
	echinococcectomy from the liver + external drainage of the gallbladder	5 (4,5%)		including	Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy + laparoscopic cholecystectomy	68 (57,1%)

	echinococcectomy from the liver without drainage gallbladder	3 (2,7%)			Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy + open cholecystectomy	47 (39,5%)
Two-stage interventions (n=6) (5,4%)	Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy → laparoscopic cholecystectomy	2 (1,8%)			Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy + laparotomy echinococcectomy from the liver	4 (3,4%)
	Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy → endoscopic nasobiliary drainage → laparoscopic cholecystectomy	1 (0,9%)				
	Endoscopic papillosphincterotomy → open cholecystectomy	3 (2,7%)				

As follows from the data in table 2, surgical interventions were performed in both single-stage and two-stage formats. In the comparison group, single-stage operations prevailed, accounting for 94.6% of cases. In the main group, single-stage interventions also dominated (56.9%), but a significant part of them were represented by hybrid operations (48.4%). Among them, endoscopic papillosphincterotomy (EPST) with litextraction from the common bile duct (choledochus) and cholecystectomy were performed most frequently, both laparoscopically (57.1%) and by open method (39.5%). In addition, hybrid interventions included EPST with removal of the chitinous membrane and daughter bladders from the bile ducts in combination with open-access liver echinococcectomy (3.4%).

The management of patients with purulent cholangitis in the Tokai classification comparison group (2013, 2018) assumed an individualized approach based on the severity of the disease. Surgical intervention was postponed until the patients' condition stabilized, especially in severe cases (Grade III).

The inclusion of plasmapheresis in combination with indirect electrochemical oxygenation and ozonation (PP with IECO+O₃) in the program of perioperative management of patients in the main group with purulent cholangitis and cholemic endotoxemia significantly improved the clinical results of treatment. The conducted studies have confirmed the high effectiveness of this technique in eliminating endogenous intoxication, reducing the risk of developing multiple organ failure and improving homeostasis.

Research results. The expansion of indications for hybrid and Rendezvous operations did not negatively affect the duration of surgical intervention. On the contrary, this indicator has decreased. The duration of inpatient treatment after surgery decreased by 2 times compared with the control – from 7.2 ± 1.2 to 5.9 ± 0.3 days.

Reducing the traumatic nature of surgical access with early activation of operated patients contributed to a twofold reduction in the duration of postoperative rehabilitation.

Compared to previous years of working with patients with acute cholangitis, we have significantly reduced the indications for surgery from the traditional wide range. This circumstance, combined with a decrease in the frequency of early postoperative complications, had a positive effect on the frequency of hospital discharge, which decreased by 5 times.

Compared to 2018-2020, the incidence of postoperative complications decreased from 26.8% to 6.1%, that is, by almost 4.5 times, and mortality decreased by 3 times. Purulent – septic complications decreased significantly from 15.2% to 2.4%, complications such as bile discharge (3.5 times) and biliary peritonitis became less common.

In 4 (4.3%) cases in the comparison group, the cause of death was multiple organ failure in patients with severe cholangitis and cholemic endotoxemia, and in 1 (1.1%) case, the cause of death was duodenal wall perforation, followed by retroperitoneal phlegmon and purulent–septic complication. In 4 (2.0%) cases in the main group, severe cholemic endotoxemia was also the cause of death. Of these, in one case, death occurred after open cholecystectomy with external drainage of the choledochus, in another case the cause of death was total pancreatic necrosis after EPST, and in two cases — at the first stage of treatment after antegrade cholangiography in patients with cicatricial stricture of hepaticocholedochus and severe cholangitis (GIII). It should be noted that in these three cases, patients did not undergo plasmapheresis sessions in combination with IECO.

In 9 patients with purulent-septic complications, such as subdiaphragmatic and subhepatic abscesses, in 4 cases it was possible to perform puncture and drainage of the purulent cavity under ultrasound control. In 5 cases, the abscess was surgically opened: according to Melnikov– in 1 case with a subdiaphragmatic abscess and through the right subcostal access with a subhepatic abscess.

In 1 case, cholemic bleeding was stopped by conservative therapy. Conservative treatment was also performed in patients with suppuration of the residual

cavity (1 patient) and postoperative wound (3 patients).

In the main group of patients, with the development of local complications after surgical interventions, only two patients required repeated operations.

One patient underwent laparotomy with ligation of the cystic duct after a hybrid operation (EPST + LHE) due to the clip slipping off the stump of the cystic duct. Another patient with suppuration of the residual cavity after echinococcectomy required a cutaneous puncture and drainage of the residual cavity under ultrasound control.

In 3 patients with purulent-septic complications, purulent focus sanitation was performed under ultrasound navigation.

In the remaining 6 cases, the complications were stopped by conservative therapy and dynamic monitoring in the presence of external bile discharge.

Conclusions: An analysis of the results of treatment of patients with acute purulent cholangitis showed that the leading factor in mortality is severe biliary endotoxemia caused by a systemic inflammatory reaction against the background of biliary tract obstruction and bile infection. The highest incidence of deaths (4.5%) and local complications (18.7%) was noted after emergency single-stage radical interventions, which is associated with high surgical trauma, significant intraoperative bacterial contamination and the inability of the patient's body to adequately compensate for the effects of endotoxemia in conditions of severe septic process.

Hybrid interventions in mild to moderate acute cholangitis with choledocholithiasis and breakthrough of echinococcal cysts into the bile ducts are an acceptable and safe alternative to traditional two-stage treatment. Stage-by-stage surgical treatment for severe purulent cholangitis and biliary endotoxemia with the use of preliminary decompressive interventions on the biliary tract made it possible to stop cholestasis and purulent intoxication, as well as improve the results of radical operations. The use of a differentiated surgical approach in these groups helped to reduce the incidence of complications from 26.8% to 6.1%, reduce the length of hospitalization and improve the quality of life of patients.

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